

A Review on Automatic Figure Vein Recognition System

Sambhaji V. Deshmukh¹ and Nitish S. Zulpe²

¹Assistant Professor, COCSIT, Latur, S.R.T.M. University, Nanded, MS, India

²Principal, COCSIT, Latur, S.R.T.M. University, Nanded, MS, India

Email: deshmukhsv3069@gmail.com, nitishzulpe@gmail.com

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Abstract

This research paper presents an extensive overview of research articles focusing on the application of DL (Deep Learning) methods for finger vein identification, recognition, and authentication systems. Over approximately eight years, spanning from 2017 to 2024, a significant surge in interest has been observed in the field of finger vein biometrics. Particularly noteworthy is the recent shift towards leveraging CNNs (Convolutional Neural Networks), mirroring the broader trend of employing models for DL across various domains. The literature analysis conducted herein delves into the exploration of non-handcrafted features learned within deep learning frameworks. Furthermore, this review critically examines the outcomes, strengths, and limitations of existing techniques, shedding light on the advancements and challenges within this rapidly evolving research area.

Keywords: Biometric systems, survey, finger vein recognition, deep learning, Convolutional Neural Networks.

Introduction

Finger vein biometric systems have garnered increasing attention due to their potential for robust and secure authentication. Leveraging advancements in deep learning, particularly CNNs, has become a prevalent approach to enhancing the accuracy and reliability of such systems. This paper proposes to provide a comprehensive overview of the research landscape, spanning approximately eight years, and elucidate the evolution towards deep learning. Biometric characteristics are unique physical or behavioral traits of individuals that can be used for identification or verification purposes. These characteristics are intrinsic to an individual and can be measured or observed to confirm their identity. [1].

Fingerprints, facial expressions, and Fingerprints are indeed common illustrations of biometric characteristics used for authentication purposes [2]. Fingerprints have several advantages when used in biometric authentication systems such as difficulty in faking, high efficiency, contactless payments, ease of use, and non-intrusive Overall fingerprint recognition offers a robust and convenient solution for biometric authentication, with widespread applications across industries such as banking, healthcare, government, and telecommunications [3-5]. However, due to the difficulty of extracting fingerprints, successful fingerprint authentication requires very efficient fingerprint sensors [6]. Because of this, the primary focus of this article is on the examination of finger veins in humans that are capable of actively recognizing an individual's biometric identification.

The majority of people are unable to compress images, and in any kind of setting, finger veins can persist [7]. Age has no bearing on vein patterns. Via the blood vessels, fingers transmit short-wavelength near-infrared light. The light is absorbed by Hb in the blood, producing the vein picture. The unique vein patterns seen in the fingers are robust and constant under all conditions [8-10]. However, it is not possible to effectively attain greater accuracy performance because of the dryness of the fingers [11]. To extract vein characteristics anywhere, effective automatic feature extraction algorithms are essential. Numerous research has been conducted [12-14] to efficiently extract vein features; nevertheless, these methods have significant over-fitting problems in the course of the training phase. The technology for automatically extracting and recognizing veins in the fingers is user-friendly and adaptable to many fingers.

Recently, the integration of AI-based techniques, including ML and DL, has significantly advanced the field of biometric recognition, leading to more accurate, robust, and efficient systems. For biometric-based finger vein detection, a variety of ML (Machine Learning)-based approaches are being researched, including SVM (Support Vector Machines) [15], DT (Decision Trees)

[16], LR (Logistic Regression) [17], NB (Naïve Bayes) [18], etc. Multiple finger vein recognition using machine learning approaches is not feasible, though, as this leads to significant over-fitting problems [19]. To address this problem, DL-based methods are presented and examined.

CNNs (Convolutional Neural Networks) [20], one of the DL-based approaches, have been documented in numerous previous investigations. Unfortunately, the dataset's collected vein images suffer greatly from low resolution, undesired blur effects, and noise. As a result, the degree of identification is greatly decreased, and efficient pre-processing steps are crucial to enhancing the visual quality of an image. As a result, the model's capacity for feature learning is improved and effectively applied in many applications related to security. To effectively examine its performance in finger vein recognition, innovative pre-emphasizing stages & an efficient DL-based model for recognition were introduced in this study.

Literature review

Ameen and Al-ogaili [21] introduced LeNet-CNN (LeNet-based Convolutional Neural Network) the DL Technique applied on 1000 vein images which were SDUMLA-HMT database, and evaluated similarity between an individual and found 97.5% accuracy.

Boucherit et al. [22] used the CLAH (Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram) technique in conjunction with the Deep Fused CNN (DF-CNN) model to improve image quality and recognition. The results showed an accuracy of 99.5% for the SDUMLA-HMT dataset and 96.7% for the FV-USM dataset.

For recognition purposes, Boucetta and Leila [23] used a SqueezeNet-based deep CNN model; for authentication, they used an SVM classifier; and for potentially relevant feature selection, they employed FL-DCA (Feature Level Discriminant Correlation Analysis). The experimental result demonstrates a 99.5% accuracy rate.

In their paper, Shaheed et al. [24] proposed the hybridized DL approach for finger vein detection and developed depthwise-separable CNN with SVM (DSCNN-SVM). Observed 0.00% is a low error rate.

Sulaiman et al. [25] introduced, the A-DRL (Attention Based Deep Regional Learning) model was used for persons' finger vein recognition which obtained an accuracy of 98.5%. Unfortunately, the study's method's inadequate feature learning power leads to substantial inaccuracy.

Because each vein is unique, Deshmukh Sambhaji [26] developed a unique finger vein recognition model

(PyDS-MV3) for person authentication. The vein characteristics are extracted quickly from pre-processed pictures using the Kernel Attentive Resnet152v2 (KAtt-ResNet152V2) approach. The best "vein features for lowering the feature dimensionalities are then chosen by feeding the extracted vein features into the Hybridized Golden Archerfish Optimizer (HyG-ArfO). To precisely identify a person's finger veins, the best features are then supplied into the Depthwise Separable MobileNetV3 (PyDS-MV3)" method, which is based on the Residual Pyramid. Table "1 displays the comparative analysis of state-of-the-art techniques.

Table 1: a comparison of current state-of-the-art methods

Method	Data Set	Performance	Merits	Demerits	Author and references
LeNet-CNN	SDUMLA-HMT	Accuracy- 97.5%	The utilization of Euclidean distance helps to recognize the	High data redundancy problems	Al-ogaili and Ameen [21]
DF-CNN	FV-USM and SDUMLA-HMT	Accuracy of 96.7% and 99.5% respectively	High accuracy and low cost approach.	High gradient vanishing problems.	Boucherit et al. [22]
squeezeNet-based deep CNN	FV-USM, and SDUMLA-HMT	Accuracy of 99.5%	Avoids gradient vanishing problems in the network model	High time complexity	Boucetta and Leila [23]
DSCNN-SVM	Idiap and SCUT-FVD	Low error rate of 0.00%	Low error rate and less computation cost.	Training with larger datasets is not applicable.	Shaheed et al. [24]
A-DRL	DUMLA-HMT	Accuracy of 98.5%	Simple and fast outcome.	Due to low feature learning capability cause high error rate.	Sulaiman et al. [25]
PyDS-MV3	Kaggle	Accuracy of 99.4%	Faster" outcome.	Possibility of Optimum level.	Deshmukh Sambhaji[26]

Discussion and Conclusion

This review concludes by highlighting the noteworthy advancements made in the use of deep learning for systems that recognize and authenticate finger veins. The shift towards CNN-based approaches has yielded notable improvements in accuracy and robustness. However, challenges such as dataset availability and

computational complexity necessitate further research efforts. By addressing these limitations, deep learning holds immense potential in advancing the state-of-the-art in finger vein biometrics, paving the way for more secure and reliable authentication systems.

This paper underscores the significance of DL-based approaches in advancing finger vein recognition technology. By overcoming the drawbacks of existing

models as well as leveraging the capabilities of deep neural networks, these approaches offer promising avenues for enhancing classification accuracy, improving model robustness, and optimizing hyperparameter configurations. The experimental validation demonstrates the efficacy of DL-based models in achieving superior performance, thereby paving the way for enhanced finger vein recognition systems in industrial and educational settings.

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Correspondence and requests for materials should be addressed to Sambhaji V. Deshmukh.

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